

Key aspects of enforcing judgments in labour disputes

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Annotation: This article analyzes the distinctive aspects of enforcing court decisions in labor disputes. It examines the fundamental principles of labor law, the legal and practical challenges encountered in executing court rulings, and international experiences in this regard. Special attention is given to the issue of repeated execution, analyzing the legal consequences arising from non-enforcement or incomplete implementation of court decisions. Additionally, the article explores judicial accountability and factors influencing the timely and complete execution of court rulings. Institutional approaches to the enforcement of court decisions, the role of state authorities, and effective solutions for resolving labor disputes are also discussed.

Keywords: labor disputes, repeated execution, discipline, accountability, annulment, ruling, employer, employee, judicial practice, enforcement document, international experience.

This article employs several methodological approaches to address the problems arising in the field of labour relations:

Normative analysis: The principal sources of labour law, namely the Labour Code as well as national and international judicial decisions, are examined.

Comparative analysis: National legislative norms are compared with international standards, and the application of foreign experience is proposed.

Empirical analysis: The practical aspects of enforcing decisions in the resolution of labour disputes, in particular the available statistical data on judicial practice, are analysed.

Systematic and structural analysis: The enforcement mechanisms relating to the execution of court decisions are examined as an integrated system.

Labour disputes occupy an important place in the legal system of any society. Disagreements between employer and employee may arise for various reasons, including working conditions, termination of the employment contract, issues related to the payment of wages, and other aspects of labour relations.

At the same time, the court system plays a crucial role in the resolution of labour disputes, while the effectiveness of the enforcement of judicial decisions is of great importance for ensuring that such disputes are settled fairly. Although court judgments possess legal force in many countries, their actual enforcement is often a complex process, and problems related to delayed or incomplete execution may arise.

In an era when legislation is steadily developing, it has become necessary to address a particular problem that causes difficulties for employers engaged in disputes with employees and to propose an appropriate solution to this issue.

A number of provisions of the Labour Code establish the employer's obligation to compensate material damage and moral harm caused to the employee, including in cases of unlawful refusal to hire (Article 120 of the Labour Code), unlawful modification of the employment contract (Article 150), unlawful suspension from work (Article 155), unlawful termination of the employment contract (Article 174), as well as in cases of violation of the procedure for processing and protecting the employee's personal data by the employer (Article 180), among others. It is evident that disputes are likely to arise in connection with the application of these norms.

One of the practical problems that arises is the following: where an employee whose employment contract has been terminated is reinstated by a court, part two of Article 174 of the Labour Code stipulates that, if the employment contract has been unlawfully terminated, the employee's claims for being provided with his or her previous job, for compensation of the material damage caused, and for compensation of

moral harm (where the unlawful termination of the employment contract has caused moral or physical suffering to the employee) must be granted. In such a situation, the employee is reinstated, and the court's decision on reinstatement and on payment of wages for a period not exceeding three months in favour of the employee must be enforced without delay, as required by Article 569 of the Labour Code.

In addition, under Article 82 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Enforcement of Judicial Documents and Documents of Other Bodies", writs of execution concerning reinstatement are to be enforced immediately by the employer vested with the power to reinstate, from the day on which the writ of execution is submitted by the claimant for enforcement.

Before the law, everyone is equal; therefore, once the employee has been reinstated, the employer must immediately execute the court's judgment from the moment the writ of execution is submitted. In accordance with the court's decision, the employee must be paid an amount equal to his or her average monthly wage for the period of forced absence from work, as well as an amount not less than his or her average monthly wage as compensation for moral harm.

In order to avoid liability under Article 198² of the Code of Administrative Liability, the employer promptly enforced the court's decision. Pursuant to part one of Article 385¹ of the Civil Procedure Code, an appeal (or protest) may be lodged within one month from the date on which the judgment was adopted by the court. Relying on this provision, the employer lodged an appeal and, by submitting additional evidence, succeeded at the appellate instance in proving that the employee's dismissal had in fact been lawful.

However, the issue that forms the subject of this article – the problem of reverse (restitutionary) execution – remains unresolved. In other words, as a result of the new evidence presented by the employer, the first-instance judgment in favour of the employee is set aside, yet the claim for compensation of material damage and moral

harm has already been enforced by the employer, and the sums paid are not being reimbursed to the employer.

According to the final part of Article 569 of the Labour Code, where judicial documents arising from individual labour relations are annulled, reverse execution of such judicial documents is permitted only if the annulled decision was based on false information reported by the claimant or on forged documents submitted by him or her. In other words, if the court decision was not adopted on the basis of false information or forged documents provided by the employee, the sums paid to the employee cannot be recovered from him or her.

In the situation under consideration, there is no answer in the legislation to the question of who should recover, in favour of the employer, the amounts paid to the employee and who should bear liability for them.

Furthermore, pursuant to part two of Article 74 of the Law “On Courts”, the annulment or modification of a court decision in itself does not entail liability of the judge who participated in adopting that decision, unless the judge intentionally allowed a violation of the law or gross negligence that led to serious consequences. This legal provision is formulated in general terms and makes the judge liable for an annulled decision only where he or she has deliberately breached the law or has allowed gross negligence leading to serious consequences; however, it does not address situations where the judge’s error is due to carelessness in the form of overconfidence. In addition, no legislative act defines the notion of “gross negligence leading to serious consequences”, which, in practice, allows this norm to be circumvented in almost any situation.

Thus, when a judgment or other judicial act is annulled, the amounts recovered in favour of the employee cannot be reclaimed either from the employee or from the court (judge). In such a situation, the only party that suffers loss is the employer, while no person can be clearly identified as liable.

According to the National News Agency of Uzbekistan, at a conference initiated by the Jizzakh Regional Court it was reported that, in 2024, district and inter-district civil courts considered a total of 703 civil cases related to labour disputes. Of these, 442 statements of claim were granted, 146 were dismissed, 94 were left without consideration, and proceedings were terminated in 21 cases.

These figures clearly show that labour disputes constitute a significant portion of civil cases, and a large share of such cases relates to reinstatement, recovery of unpaid amounts and similar claims.

The root cause of the problem currently under analysis lies in the fact that judges do not play an active role in civil courts. Under Article 10 of the Civil Procedure Code, civil proceedings are conducted on the basis of the adversarial principle and equality of the parties. As a result, the party that presents stronger evidence effectively dominates the civil case. In other words, the court assesses the case on the basis of the materials submitted by the parties, which leaves the judge in a largely passive position within the ongoing civil proceedings.

In contrast, pursuant to Article 11 of the Code of Administrative Judicial Procedure, proceedings in administrative courts are conducted on the basis of the active role of the court. This significantly enhances the fairness of the proceedings, since, in the course of adjudication, the judge is empowered not only to assess the parties' arguments but also to request additional evidence. In particular, the court, on its own initiative or at the request of the parties, collects additional evidence and undertakes other actions aimed at fulfilling the tasks of administrative judicial proceedings.

Such a practice is found in a number of European countries, including Austria, Belgium, Denmark and others, where courts play an active role in the examination of labour disputes.

In civil courts, employers often lose cases because they fail to pay due attention to evidence that could fundamentally influence the outcome of the proceedings, and as a

result they are ordered to pay compensation in favour of the employee in amounts reaching millions or even billions. However, at a higher instance, based on additional evidence submitted, the civil case may be resolved in favour of the employer. Unfortunately, it then becomes practically impossible to recover from the employee the sums previously awarded and paid in his or her favour. In reality, in such cases civil judges are often able to foresee in advance in whose favour the case should rightly be decided, yet, due to the absence of an active judicial role in this procedural model, they become mere witnesses to an unjust outcome.

For this reason, it appears advisable to introduce, in civil courts as well, an active role for judges similar to that established in administrative courts. Indeed, increased judicial activism in the conduct of proceedings would make it possible to prevent various violations of the law and would give the court the opportunity to request necessary evidence from the parties on its own initiative. In addition, putting forward new conceptual approaches regarding the issue of reverse execution would allow corresponding amendments and improvements to be proposed for the legislative framework.

References:

1. Labour Code.
2. Code of Administrative Liability.
3. Civil Procedure Code.
4. Code of Administrative Judicial Procedure.
5. Law “On Enforcement of Judicial Documents and Documents of Other Bodies”.
6. Law “On Courts”.